

A Lecture Experiment on Gas Diffusion.

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In order to demonstrate the change of pressure resulting from the different rates of diffusion of gases, the use of Cartesian divers has been found to be effective. Two coloured divers, so adjusted that one just sinks and the other just floats, are separated by a glass plate in a tall gas jar full of water. The rubber hung in the jar carries a tube strong enough to support the weight of a porous pot, which is held mouth upwards by the tube being bent twice at right angles over a short length. On placing a vessel of hydrogen over the pot, the top diver sinks. On removing it both rise. By bringing a vessel of carbon dioxide up under the pot the bottom diver rises.

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